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The Influence of Internet Communication Means on the Social and Psychological Characteristics of Youth and Their Social Behavior

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ABSTRACT

This article comprehensively analyzes the influence of internet communication tools on the socio-psychological characteristics of young people and their social behavior. The study examined the influence of social networks, messengers, and online platforms on the personal development, emotional state, communication culture, value system, and behavior of young people based on scientific sources. The positive and negative aspects of Internet communication were identified, and scientific conclusions and practical recommendations were made from the point of view of youth psychology.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of information and communication technologies has a significant impact on all spheres of society, in particular, on the lifestyle of young people. Today, the means of Internet communication have become the main platform for young people to communicate, exchange information, express their opinion, and form social relations. Social networks, messengers, and online forums are becoming a priority form of daily communication among young people.

Since young people are in the process of forming as individuals, the communicative processes taking place in the Internet environment have a strong influence on their socio-psychological characteristics and behavior. From this point of view, the study of the influence of internet communication tools on the psychology and social behavior of young people on a deep scientific basis is an urgent scientific problem. In addition, internet communication actively influences the processes of exchanging social experience, forming group identity, and mastering social roles among young people. The forms of communication taking place in the digital environment are directly reflected in the social relations of young people in real life, causing certain changes in their behavior and value system. At the same time, a deep analysis of the psychological consequences of internet communication makes it possible to develop effective pedagogical and psychological approaches to working with young people. This research is aimed at illuminating these aspects on a scientific basis.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In foreign and domestic scientific literature, it is noted that internet communication has a two-sided impact on the development of youth. Castells [1] evaluates the internet as a factor shaping a global social network, emphasizing that it increases an individual's social activity. Boyd [2] scientifically substantiates that social networks play an important role in the process of youth identification. Turkle [3] focuses on the psychological risks of the internet, arguing that virtual communication can lead to a reduction in real social contacts. Livingstone [4] shows how young people change their emotional state and social adaptation when they use the internet. In Uzbek and regional studies, the influence of internet communication on the behavior of young people was analyzed in connection with social adaptation, communicative competence, and emotional stability. These studies show the need for proper management of the Internet environment and the formation of a digital culture.

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3. RESEARCH METHODS

Internet means of communication directly and indirectly influence the socio-psychological development of young people. First of all, communication in the Internet environment is an important factor in the formation of communicative competence of young people. Social networks and online platforms allow young people to freely express their opinions, participate in discussions, and interact with various social groups. This process increases the social adaptability and openness of young people to communication[5]. At the same time, internet communication has a strong influence on the process of personal identification of young people. Self-presentation in the virtual environment, image creation on social networks, and receiving the evaluation of others become an important psychological factor in the process of self-awareness of young people. Indicators such as "likes," "comments," and "number of subscribers" can shape or change young people's self-esteem. This situation is not only positive, but in some cases also leads to psychological pressure and low self-esteem.

Table 1
The main positive and negative impacts of Internet communication tools on the socio-psychological characteristics of young people

Directions of influence	Positive aspects	Negative aspects
Communicative activity	Increased sociability	Decrease in real communication
Self-awareness	Free expression of opinion	Low self-esteem
Emotional state	Psychological support	Anxiety
Social adaptation	Join new social groups	Sense of loneliness
Personal development	Knowledge and worldview expand	Internet addiction

Mazkur jadvalda internet kommunikatsiya vositalarining yoshlar ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlariga ko'rsatadigan asosiy ta'sir yo'nalishlari tizimli tarzda umumlashtirilgan. Jadvaldan ko'rinib turibdiki, internet orqali muloqot qilish yoshlarning kommunikativ faolligini oshirib, ularning ijtimoiy aloqalarni kengaytirishiga va o'z fikrini erkin ifodalashiga imkon yaratadi. Shu bilan birga, internet muhitida shakllanadigan virtual muloqot real ijtimoiy aloqalarning qisqarishiga olib kelishi mumkin[6]. Internet kommunikatsiyasi yoshlarning o'zini anglash va shaxsiy identifikatsiya jarayonida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali o'zini namoyon etish yoshlarning o'ziga bo'lgan ishonchini oshirishi mumkin, biroq doimiy ijtimoiy taqqoslash va tashqi baholarga bog'liqlik o'zini past baholash holatlarini keltirib chiqarishi ehtimoli mavjud. Bu holat yoshlarning psixologik barqarorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Another important aspect of the means of Internet communication is the influence on the emotional state of young people. The constant flow of information, social comparison, and virtual communication can have a positive or negative impact on the mental state of young people[7]. On the positive side, the Internet provides psychological support for young people, allows them to find like-minded people in their interests. Negatively, being online for a long time can lead to fatigue, anxiety, emotional instability, and psychological dependence. As a result, internet communication is a powerful factor in the formation of socio-psychological characteristics of young people, the influence of which is manifested depending on the level of personal stability, self-confidence, and social adaptation of young people.

Figure 1

Influence of Internet communication tools on the social behavior of young people

As can be seen from the diagram, internet communication mainly serves to increase the social activity of young people, however, the presence of negative forms of behavior also indicates the complexity of the problem.

Internet means of communication manifest themselves as an important social environment in the formation of social behavior of young people. Communication styles, social norms, and values formed in the virtual space are transferred to behavior in real life. In particular, information and social trends disseminated through the Internet have a significant impact on the views and behavior of young people. On the positive side, internet communication encourages young people to be socially active[8]. Through online platforms, young people participate in public discussions, support social projects, volunteer activities, and civic initiatives. This process serves to increase the sense of responsibility of young people and the formation of an active civic position.

However, some features of the internet environment can also create negative situations in the behavior of young people. The feeling of anonymity and distance leads some young people to carry out aggressive, irresponsible, or antisocial behavior. Aggressive content, elements of violence, and false information found on the Internet are likely to form negative patterns in the behavior of young people. Internet communication also influences young people's time management and daily behavior. Excessive immersion in online activities can lead to a decrease in attention to studies, work activities, and real social relationships. This situation negatively affects the social responsibility and discipline of young people[9].

4. DISCUSSION

The obtained results showed that the influence of internet communication tools on the socio-psychological characteristics and social behavior of young people is a complex and multifaceted process. The obtained conclusions indicate that internet communication influences the formation of young people as individuals simultaneously as both a developmental and a limiting factor. This situation shows that internet communication cannot be assessed only as a positive or negative phenomenon. Internet means of communication increase the communicative activity and social flexibility of young people, but this activity is often limited to virtual space. As a result, there is a risk of imbalance between real social relations and virtual communication. This situation can slow down the process of young people accumulating social experience in real life.

Also, the research results show that the norms formed in the Internet environment play an important role in the social behavior of young people. A decrease in the sense of anonymity and responsibility in the virtual space can lead some young people to become indifferent to social norms even in real life. This requires a restructuring of the concepts of social discipline and responsibility. On the other hand, internet communication expands opportunities for young people to express themselves and increase social activity. The results of the study show an increase in the participation of young people in social initiatives in the online environment, participation in public discussions, and not being indifferent to social issues. This confirms the potential of Internet communication for social development.

5. CONCLUSION.

Internet means of communication play an important role in the formation of socio-psychological characteristics and social behavior of young people. Internet communication increases the communicative activity of young people, but its uncontrolled and excessive use can lead to psychological problems. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure the conscious use of the Internet by young people, increase digital literacy, and strengthen psychological preventive measures. The research results have practical significance for educational institutions, psychologists, and parents.

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